

Spatial Motion in Quantum Mechanics and Wavefunction Squared as Density

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In a previous note, it was argued one could construct an expression for $P(p/x)$, the probability for a momentum p at x , and then by using formulas from statistics show that physical density in quantum mechanics equals the wavefunction squared. In this argument, the wavefunction $W(x)$ is an x dependent normalization constant for an expression of average kinetic energy at a point x , namely $[\text{Sum on } p \ p^2/2m \ f_p \sin(px)] / W(x)$. Here f_p is a probability weight to have a momentum p and it was noted that $W(x)$ and f_p are Fourier transforms of each other. In this note, we wish to attempt to examine two points. First, it seems a little confusing that one sums over all possible momenta at a point x . We would like to see if there could be a reason for this. Secondly, we wish to obtain the result: spatial density = wavefunction squared in terms of a picture of dynamics so that there is some idea of what is happening at a microscopic level in quantum mechanics.

Formulation of the Time Independent Schrodinger Equation

In (1), a derivation of the time-independent Schrodinger equation was attempted by calculating the average kinetic energy at a point x . This approach assumes that a particle can exist at a point, which is a classical assumption. In (1), it was also argued that the quantum particles undergo a type of zitterbewegung or forward and backward motion while having an overall average velocity in one direction. Thus, a particle is spread out over space at least over a length of the wavelength. The particle, however, need not have equal probability of being at each point within the wavelength. Thus, it seems that one can use the idea of a particle having a probability to be at a point, even though the particle is undergoing some kind of periodic motion within a length of the wavelength. This is important if one is to use $V(x)$, the classical potential at a point x . If one has one particle at x , the potential energy is $V(x)$. The next step is to create an average kinetic energy at x . It was argued in (1), that if one places a particle, with momentum p and zitterbewegung, in a potential, there will be all kinds of scattering occurring. Given that a particle with a momentum p can exist within a wavelength, it is not clear at which point an interaction with $V(x)$ will occur within this wavelength. Thus, the idea of having one p value at given x does not seem to make sense (as it does in classical mechanics).

With these ideas, let us write an average kinetic energy at a point x as in (1):

$$\text{KE average at } x = [\text{Sum on } p \ p^2/2m \ f_p \sin(px)] / W(x) \quad ((1))$$

Here f_p is a weight to have a momentum p , $\sin(px)$ models the oscillatory probability of zitterbewegung particle and $W(x) = \text{Sum over } p \ f_p \sin(px)$, is a normalization constant which depends on x . It should be noted that $\sin(px)$ implies oscillatory motion in exactly the same manner in both x and p space. This is important for quantum mechanics. KE average at x is the average kinetic energy of a particle at x thus if it is added to $V(x)$ one should obtain E the total

energy, by conservation of energy. As argued in (1), this is also the time-independent Schrodinger equation.

It should be noted that in ((1)), at each point x , one actually sums over all possible momentum values. It is important to have some kind of idea what is happening as there is also the factor $\exp(iEt)$ with E being the eigenenergy. This factor suggests that there is a cycling process occurring. In (1) it was argued that in the time-independent Schrodinger equation, the term $V(x)W(x)$, where $W(x)$ is the wavefunction involves interactions between the potential and $W(x)$. In other words, one can write $V(x)$ as a Fourier series and $W(x)$ as another Fourier series. For $W(x)$ one has $\sum_{p \neq 0} \frac{1}{2i} (\exp(ipx) - \exp(-ipx))$. In $W(x)$, one interprets $\exp(-ipx)$ as a forward moving wave, thus one should have a similar interpretation of terms in the Fourier series of $V(x)$. Thus, it seems that "waves" carrying momentum in the potential can combine with the waves in the wavefunction. Thus, a quantum bound state seems to be a kind of resonance between the potential and the particle. The cycling $\exp(iEt)$ shows how the system shifts from one p state to another i.e. $\sum_{p \neq 0} \sin(px)$ to create this oscillatory resonance. This is very different from the picture of classical mechanics. There as one gains potential energy one loses kinetic energy. In quantum mechanics, as one gains potential energy, the average kinetic energy drops, but there are still all sorts of combinations of various p values available. This may also be related to tunneling as the resonance with $V(x)$ may provide for large p bursts (with low probability) which would allow for the penetration of a barrier. This may also explain why, even for large energy eigenvalues (say in the case of the oscillator), the quantum spatial density still exhibits humps, while the classical density is a smooth $1/v(x)$, where $v(x)$ is the average velocity at point x .

Spatial Density as Wavefunction Squared

It was argued in (2) that:

$$P(p/x) = \text{probability to have a } p \text{ at } x = \frac{\sum_{p \neq 0} \sin(px)}{W(x)} \quad ((2))$$

One should note that $\sum_{p \neq 0} P(p/x) = 1$, but that this probability allows negative values.

Next, the relations $P(p/x) = P(x \text{ intersection } p) / P(x)$ and $P(x/p) = P(x \text{ intersection } p) / P(p)$ were used and $P(x \text{ intersection } p)$ was eliminated enroute to attempting to show that spatial density $P(x)$ equals $W(x) \cdot W(x)$. Here we wish to examine $P(x \text{ intersection } p)$ to try to see what is happening. In ((2)), we have the idea that there is a weight $\sum_{p \neq 0}$ to have a momentum p and a $W(x)$ normalization weight at each point x . Writing $P(x/p) = [W(x) \sum_{p \neq 0} \sin(px)] / \sum_{p \neq 0} \sin(px)$ we see that $W(x)$ is a weight to be at a position x . Thus, to have a p and x together it seems that one can write:

$$P(x \text{ intersection } p) = W(x) \sum_{p \neq 0} \sin(px)$$

Here, $\sum_{p \neq 0} \sin(px)$ is the probability from zitterbewegung, assuming that one can model it as a sine function.

If this is a probability, one will need to be careful about normalization. If one sums over p one obtains $W(x)W(x)$ or the spatial density. If one sums over x , one obtains $\int p^2 dp$ the probability to have a momentum p . One needs the restrictions that the integral of $W(x)W(x)$ is one and the integral over p is $\int p^2 dp$ is 1.

Thus, it seems that at a given point x , one can consider a sum over the one dimensional p axis, namely $\sum_p \int p^2 dp \sin(px)$. One can, however, sum over the x axis. In such a case, as one moves along the one dimensional x axis, one has $W(x) \sin(px)$. $\sin(px)$ is the regular oscillatory motion due to zitterbewegung motion, but $W(x)$ is a quantum mechanical amplitude which is changing with x . Thus, if one wanted to calculate averages throughout space one could write expressions such as $\sum_p \int p^2 dp W(x) \sin(px)$ or $\sum_p \int p^2 dp W(x) \sin(px)$. These represent kinetic energy density or momentum density expressions and seem to show how quantum mechanics differs from regular statistical mechanics. In regular statistical mechanics there is no weight $W(x)$ at each point x , as well as no $\sin(px)$ zitterbewegung factor. (In quantum mechanics, this extra weight $W(x)$ appears on the left hand side of an expectation value statement $\langle W(x) | \hbar^2 \nabla^2 / 2m | W(x) \rangle$). Thus, it seems that one must be careful when considering microscopic fluxes in quantum mechanics as there is a weight $W(x)$ at each point associated with the flux. Nevertheless the idea of flux seems to be present as $d/dx W(x)W(x) = \text{change in density} = 2 W(x) d/dx W(x)$. Microscopically this is : $2 W(x) \sum_p \int p^2 dp \sin(px)$. Here one sees the statistical mechanical flux with the additional weights of $W(x)$ and $\sin(px)$. For the case of the oscillator, it is interesting to note that $d/dx W(x)$ gives $v(x) W(x)$ where $v(x)$ is the classical v at point x or the quantum mechanical root mean square average at x . Thus, a flux $W(x) d/dx W(x)$ in quantum mechanics matches that of statistical mechanics for this case.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we have attempted to argue that a quantum mechanical bound state is a resonance between a particle with zitterbewegung and a potential $V(x)$. The potential supplies many momentum p components which appear in quantum mechanical averages. We have also tried to argue that the spatial density in quantum mechanics can be obtained directly from $P(x, p)$ with weights $W(x)$ and $\int p^2 dp$ appearing for x and p respectively, together with a zitterbewegung factor of $\sin(px)$. Thus, we argue that as a quantum particle moves through space, one must include two factors $W(x)$ and $\sin(px)$. Thus, instead of writing $\int p^2 dp$ for the kinetic energy, one would write $W(x) \int p^2 dp \sin(px)$ when calculating a space average. One can similarly write a quantum mechanical flux, namely $W(x) \int p^2 dp \sin(px)$.

References

1. Ruggeri, Francesco R. 2x2 Matrix Model and the Schrodinger Equation (zenodo, preprint, 2018)
2. Ruggeri, Francesco R. Spatial Density as Wavefunction Squared (zenodo, preprint, 2018).